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A review of literature to identify the benefits and barriers of advanced diabetes technology use among adolescent patients diagnosed with type 1 diabetes mellitus

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Abstract:

Diabetes mellitus is one of the most common chronic endocrine diseases encountered by primary care providers in today's practice setting. The incidence of newly diagnosed type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) patients has increased and is expected to triple in the coming years. Complications of diabetes includes microvascular and macrovascular disease leading to a host of problems and poor outcomes for the patient diagnosed with diabetes. Vascular damage can begin early in the disease process and is often undetected until a major event occurs. T1DM is a lifelong diagnosis requiring strict adherence to therapy for glycemic control. Glycemic control is considered to be the cornerstone of therapy for prevention of complications and poor outcomes. Advanced diabetes technology such as insulin pump therapy and continuous glucose monitoring has shown to improve glycemic control among patients diagnosed with diabetes. This review of literature is aimed at identifying the benefits and barriers of advanced diabetes technology use among adolescent patients diagnosed with T1DM.

Keywords:

Advanced diabetes technology, insulin pump therapy, continuous glucose monitoring, patient satisfaction, quality of life, type 1 diabetes mellitus and treatment options

1. Introduction:

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is characterized by elevated blood glucose levels, known as hyperglycemia, resulting from defects in insulin secretion, insulin action, or both (Huether & McCance, 2017). In the case of T1DM there is usually an absolute insulin deficiency due to beta-cell destruction (Huether & McCance, 2017). Diabetes mellitus, whether it be type 1 diabetes (T1D), type 2 diabetes (T2D), or gestational DM, is one of the most common chronic endocrine diseases seen in primary care (Wherrett, Huot, Mitchell, & Pacaud, 2013). The incidence of newly diagnosed T1DM has increased over the years and is expected to triple by 2050 (Fortin, Pries, & Kwon, 2016). According to the Centers for Disease Control (CDC) 2014 report, more than 15,000 children are diagnosed with T1DM per year in the United States alone (<http://www.cdc.gov>). T1DM is a lifelong diagnosis that requires adherence to therapy 24 hours a day, 365 days a year, there are no vacation days. Without good glycemic control, microvascular complications can occur. Microvascular complications are of major concern because these complications affect small blood vessels and are known to lead to the three biggest concerns of microvascular disease: retinopathy, nephropathy, and neuropathy (Egan, 2016; Fortin et al., 2016; Pickett, 2016). These microvascular complications can lead to a host of problems for the diabetic patient causing blindness, heart disease, poor wound healing that leads to amputations, and kidney failure that can eventually cause patients to be placed on dialysis. A synthesis of the literature for the benefits and possible barriers of advanced diabetes technology equipment use are presented throughout the remaining sections of this paper.

2. Review of literature:

In a review of the literature, a Galileo search through the online library of a local university was conducted to obtain much of the literature used in this paper. Several key search terms were used including: advanced diabetes technology, insulin pump therapy, continuous glucose monitoring, patient satisfaction, quality of life, T1DM and treatment options, which returned a result of hundreds of thousands of articles. By narrowing the search using the advanced search feature to include advanced diabetes technology and patient satisfaction, advanced diabetes technology and quality of life, insulin pump therapy and T1DM and patient satisfaction, as well as continuous glucose monitors and T1DM and patient satisfaction, the search results were narrowed to around

5,000 articles with each advance search. Further exclusion was applied to only include articles published within the last five years, and only scholarly, peer reviewed articles of full text availability. The article numbers were reduced to just over 2,500. Diabetes care is a topic that has been well researched; limitations did surface when trying to locate research on patient satisfaction of treatment options.

The focus of the review of literature will be on the impact of advanced diabetes technology use such as an insulin pump and a continuous glucose monitor (CGM) in the adolescent T1DM patient in reference to glycemic control and quality of life.

3. Impact of advanced diabetes technology use:

Insulin pumps and continuous glucose monitors are advanced diabetes technology devices that may lead to improved glycemic control compared to traditional insulin injections with self-monitoring of blood glucose (Sheikh, Bartz, Lyons, & DeSalvo, 2018). Without consist use of these devices, benefits are minimal, and leaving the T1D patient at risk for long-term diabetes related complications.

3.1. Glycemic control:

Good glycemic control is the cornerstone of treatment and is the difference between a lives with verses a life without diabetes related microvascular complications. As little as just a 1% decrease in HbA1c has been shown to reduce microvascular complications (Pickett, 2016; Drotar et al., 2012). Through many meta-analysis and research studies, it is now clear that vascular disease for the T1DM patient begins in childhood and progresses silently until complications, such as stroke or myocardial infarction, appear (Jamiolkowska et al., 2016). Patients are often asymptomatic for microvascular complications until the disease is advanced (Pickett, 2016). The risk for coronary heart morality in T1DM patients is seven times higher than individuals without diabetes and two times higher when compared to the risk of patients with T2DM (Pickett, 2016). Pickett (2016) and Egan (2017) both reported on the longitudinal study, The Diabetes Control and Complications Trial, which studied over 1,000 patients with T1DM over a 10-year period and found a significant risk reduction of microvascular complications for patients who were treated for intense glycemic control. The intensive glycemic control group was shown to have a seventy-six percent reduction in retinopathy, a sixty percent reduction in neuropathy, and a fifty percent reduction in nephropathy

(Egan, 2017; Pickett, 2016). With appropriate glycemic control, significant risk reduction for the development of microvascular complications can be achieved (Egan, 2017). By taking advantage of CGM technology, trend information and frequent glucose sampling, patients can make lifestyle adjustments and therapeutic changes to improve their glycemic control (Klonoff et al., 2017). CGMs were developed with the intent of improving outcomes for the patient with diabetes; especially lowering hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) levels with less frequent hypoglycemic events (Klonoff et al., 2017; Marvicsin, Jennings, & Ziegler-Bezaire, 2017; Van Beers et al., 2015). Numerous studies have demonstrated lower HbA1c benefits from using CGMs with one study showing a 0.5% improvement in HbA1c levels and a decrease in the incidence of hypoglycemia (Klonoff et al., 2017). A recent meta-analysis of six randomized controlled trials confirmed that HbA1c levels decreased significantly in patients who engaged in more frequent CGM use (Gonder-Frederick et al., 2016). Bukara-Radujkovic, Miljkovic, and Lakic (2018) reported on their study of 24 patients, ages 5-18, showing that continued CGM use significantly decreased HbA1d levels as much as 0.84%. In their study HbA1c levels were measured at baseline and then again 3 months after continued CGM use, and once more at 6 months with CGM use being discontinued for the last 3 months of treatment (Bukara-Radujkovic et al., 2018). HbA1c levels showed a significant decrease after 3 months of continued CGM use and a significant increase with discontinuing CGM use for 3 months of therapy (Bukara-Radujkovic et al., 2018). This proves that continued CGM use among T1D patient's results in improved outcomes as evident by decreased HbA1c levels. As with any tool, CGMs can only improve glycemic control if it is used consistently. The Juvenile Diabetes Research Foundation (JDRF) provided evidence of this in their REALTREND trial, where the impact on HbA1c was significantly improved with frequent CGM use, ≥ 6 days/week, but not in those patients who wore the CGM < 6 days/week (Klonoff et al., 2017).

3.2. Quality of life:

The efficacy of diabetes treatment should not be evaluated solely by HbA1c levels, but should also include other aspects such as patient-reported outcomes, patient satisfaction, wellbeing, and quality of life (QOL) (Saisho, 2018). CGM use versus self-monitoring of blood glucose (SMBG) provides patients with BG trend information about direction and rate of changes (Klonoff, Ahn, & Drincic, 2017). Most RT-CGMs have the capability to sound alarms to warn patients of low, high, falling, or rising BG levels, whereas SMBG does not (Klonoff, et al., 2017). This can save the patient from experiencing damaging low or high BG levels, therefore improving his/her QOL.

Klonoff et al. (2017) reported on a survey study of almost 900 CGM users where 3 major QOL factors emerged: perceived control over diabetes, hypoglycemic safety and interpersonal support. A meta-analysis comparing multiple daily injections (MDI) and continuous subcutaneous insulin infusion (CSII) concluded that hypoglycemia was reduced by 75% with CSII therapy, as well as a reduction of diabetic ketoacidosis (DKA) (Gonder-Frederick et al., 2016). CGM use may also have psychosocial benefits, improving QOL and treatment satisfaction. Greater patient satisfaction will enhance patients' self-efficacy and adherence to therapy, leading to the achievement of long-term stable glycemic control, reduced risk of long-term diabetic complications, and an increased QOL among T1D patients (Saisho, 2018). Ruiz-de-Adana et al. (2015) evaluated QOL, glycemic control as measured by HbA1c levels, rate of hypoglycemia, and DKA among CSII users and patients on MDI that had a diagnosis of T1D and consistent CGM use. There was a significant improvement in reported QOL among CSII users, as well as a 0.5% decrease in recorded HbA1c levels, improved glycemic variability, decreased insulin requirements, increased periods of normoglycemia measured with CGM when compared to patients on MDI therapy (Ruiz-de-Adana et al., 2015). Gonder-Frederick et al. (2016) reported on a survey of 877 T1DM patients who consistently used CGMs and found that most reported an increased feeling of safety from hypoglycemia during physical activity, sleeping, and driving, as well as improved motivation and self-efficacy in diabetes self-care. Other studies found that CGM use was associated with less diabetes-related burden, decreased fear of hypoglycemia, and increased treatment satisfaction improving a patients overall QOL (Gonder-Frederick et al., 2016; Ruiz-de-Adana et al., 2015; Van Beers et al., 2015).

3.3. Limitations:

Advanced technology does not come without its limitations. Klonoff et al. (2017) point out that one disadvantage of CGMs compared to SMBG is that CGMs occasionally fail or generate outlier data and need calibration with a finger stick. In December 2016, the FDA approved the first CGM for treatment decisions, the Dexcom G, before this date CGMs were only approved for adjunctive use, meaning treatment decisions should not be based on the CGM data alone (Klonoff et al., 2017). This defeats the purpose behind the CGM technology, if you cannot provide treatment based on the results, then what is the validity. It is good that technology improvements are headed in a direction where equipment validity is being tested and approved. Future development aims to require less frequent calibration, last longer, be smaller and less obtrusive, be more accurate, and

integrate more closely with pumps to create closed loop systems utilizing additional input from non-glucose sensors (Klonoff et al., 2017).

4. Barriers to advanced diabetes technology use:

During childhood, patients with T1DM are reliant on an informal caregiver such as a parent or guardian for day-to-day disease management; but, upon entering adolescence, these patients are expected to adopt a greater role in their self-management (Bedrossian et al., 2016). Unfortunately, adolescents often have difficulty adhering to such rigid management regimens and fall to poor health outcomes (Bedrossian et al., 2016). We are in a world where the use of technology is rapidly advancing; and, plays a significant role in the day-to-day management of diabetes, possibly more so than in any other chronic disease. There is a need for advanced diabetes technology that addresses the social and technical aspects of the developing teenager. Naranjo, Tanenbaum, Iturralde, and Hood (2016) identified several barriers to technology uptake and continued use such as lack of education about technology, depression, infrequent monitoring of BG, female gender, coming from single parent families, older age at diagnosis, more severe hypoglycemic events, physical discomfort of wearing the device, difficulty with insertion/adhesives/sensor function, frequency of alarms, skin reactions to sensors, and interference with physical activity. Many times parents and adolescents have different perception for nonuse. Naranjo et al. (2016) reported that one major CGM trial revealed that parents felt the reason their adolescent resisted using a CGM was due to body image concerns, whereas the adolescents attributed nonuse to more practical issues such as insertion pain and frequent alarms. Whereas Franklin's (2016) meta-analysis did show that body image concerns were more pronounced in females, who report more self-consciousness from wearing advanced diabetes devices and the inevitable questions that arise, explaining the higher rate of discontinuation among adolescent girls. Advanced diabetes technology does offer flexibility and the potential for a more normal lifestyle, but is a constant reminder of their diabetes (Franklin, 2016). Bedrossian et al. (2016) conducted a study with ten adolescents, ages 11-17, and their caregivers to learn more about each individual's role in the day-to-day management of T1D and interactions with technology and their physical environment. Recommendations from their study included design improvements that focused on customization, integration with currently available technologies, accessibility while maintaining security, and diabetes education (Bedrossian et al., 2016). These findings provided their group with insight for

needed remote monitoring features that must be properly addressed in order to ease the transition to more self-management and promote long-term adherence among adolescent T1D patients (Bedrossian et al., 2016). A major issue to long-term usage of advanced diabetes technologies is patient acceptance. Many barriers are psychological and behavioral factors that influence individual motivation, capability, and decisions regarding technology use (Gonder-Frederick, Shepard, Grabman, & Ritterband, 2016). Technology has come a long way, but improvements are still needed to encourage increased patient compliance. Liberman, Buckingham and Phillip (2011) addresses this issue in their article titled Technology and the Human Factor, stating that there is no doubt that technology has changed the life of patients with T1DM in the last few decades, but despite the availability of all this new equipment and technology, they are still not being well utilized by many patients. It is important to understand why the technology is not always utilized and to try to find new ways to maximize the use and benefits from the technology to as many patients as possible (Liberman et al., 2011). Psychobehavioral and sociotechnical perspectives recognize the interactions between positive patient experiences and technology success, realizing that the greatest barrier to advanced technology's potential are human factors that limit adoption and effective use (Gonder-Frederick et al., 2016). Despite their potential benefits, uptake for these technologies has been limited and is demonstrated by the T1D Exchange Registry listing 60% of patients as insulin pump users and only 11% as CGM users (Sheikh et al., 2018). Long-term advanced diabetes technology use is difficult to achieve, particularly for youth and young adults and may be due to behavior barriers contributing to the technology's hassle factor identified by some as false alarms, sensor discomfort or failure, and discrepancies (Gonder-Frederick et al., 2016). Advanced diabetes technology designs require a balancing act, where tradeoffs such as accuracy (requiring frequent calibration) vs. convenience (requiring minimal calibration), and comfort (smaller size) vs capabilities (larger battery, more wireless communication protocols) (Klonoff et al., 2017). It is important to understand the benefits most important to patients, and identify factors that influence motivation and decisions to adopt these technologies; furthermore, it should be noted that decreasing barriers depends largely on technology development itself (Gonder-Frederick et al., 2016). Problems related to negative patient experiences (limited usefulness, benefits, and convenience) can be overcome through technology engineering and design (Gonder-Frederick et al., 2016). It is essential for future diabetes technology research to address these barriers since the benefits are largely dependent on patient's consistent use of the technology (Gonder-Frederick et al., 2016). A more patient centered approach is needed in diabetes

technology research and an increasing appreciation for the fundamental role of patient experience (Gonder-Frederick et al., 2016).

4.1. Insulin pump therapy:

A multiyear follow-up of 101 youth who used CSII found a discontinuation rate of 18%, with DKA, burnout, and infusion site problems as the main reasons (Gonder-Frederick et al., 2016). Study results also found that those who discontinued CSII use had significantly higher HbA1c levels, and also a significantly lower SMGB frequency. Reidy, Bracher, Foster, Vassilev, and Rogers (2017) conducted a meta-analysis to determine what influences the incorporation, adaptation and use of insulin pump therapy into the everyday lives of people living with diabetes. Three themes emerged which were of relevance: tensions between expectations and experiences in adoption and early adaptation; negotiation of responsibility and accessing support; and reflexivity, active experimentation and feedback (Reidy et al., 2017). Areas for intervention to improve insulin pump therapy among T1D patients included establishing who is responsible for management task of the device and enabling navigation to further means of support and resources (Reidy et al., 2017). Saarinen, Fernstrom, Brorsson, and Olinder (2014) conducted a study describing the transition from MDI to CSII among T1D patients and discovered most patients felt a greater sense of freedom from the day-to-day demands of T1D; but, also described the CSII as a constant reminder of their disease, exposing themselves to others, as “a sense of diabetes made visible” (p. 38). Technical difficulties and reactions of those around them were listed at the most reported negative experiences with CSII (Saarinen et al., 2014). Some patients object to being tethered to a piece of equipment due to physical or psychological discomfort or privacy concerns (Klonoff et al., 2017). Perry, James, Steinbeck, Dunbabin, and Lowe (2017) reported on their study that explored young people’s attitudes, perceptions, and experiences with diabetes management comparing CSII user to non-users and found that CSII was not being used to its fullest potential. The survey included 107 adolescents, ages 12-18, and their parents/guardians; revealing opportunities for service support enhancements and redesign to align to patient’s goals and preferences maximizing patient adherence (Perry et al., 2017).

4.2. Continuous glucose monitor (CGM):

Lawson et al. (2014) states that the effectiveness of CGM technology is directly linked to CGM adherence, which can be challenging to maintain in children and adolescents. In 2016, T1D

Exchange reported that out of over 17,000 of their T1DM patients, only 15% were using CGMs (Klonoff et al., 2017). There is really no question as to whether or not the use of CGMs and/or insulin pumps benefit patients with T1DM, many studies have shown that patients who use these advanced technology devices have better glycemic control with improved outcomes. The question I have is why do some patients choose not to utilize this equipment despite these findings. Ramchandani and Heptulla (2012) point out that glycemic benefits of real-time continuous glucose monitoring (RT-CGM) are seen in patients of all ages with 76% of sensor users admitting to better management of their diabetes with the use of RT-CGM; but, only 21% of patient's admitting to continuous use of the RT-CGM. That is more than half (55%) of sensor users believing that the RT-CGM helped them, but choosing to discontinue use or not using consistently, why? Ramchandani and Heptulla (2012) found the major reported reasons for disuse of the RT-CGM was that patients found the devices annoying, a hassle, and interfering with their lives. In my doctor of nursing practice (DNP) project I aim to further define these reasons and try to identify what is it exactly that causes the RT-CGM to be annoying, feel like a hassle, and interfere with the lives of some T1DM patients. MPharm, MPharm, Kayyali, and ElShaer (2019) reported on a survey conducted in Canada of current and advanced technologies of blood glucose monitoring and found that over 75% of patients expressed their desire for a noninvasive monitoring device. The most favorable noninvasive CGM was the wristband, with contact lenses, tattoos, and earlobe sensors also being reported as preferred noninvasive CGM technologies (MPhar et al., 2019). Advanced diabetes technology has the potential to improve self-management among T1D adolescents, but some issues regarding design still exist; resulting in the need for technology improvements, and a better understanding of and tailoring to the user is necessary in order to increase adoption rates, boost user satisfaction, and positively influence self-management (Bedrossian et al., 2016).

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